

WDM Transmission Utilizing White-LEDs: Wavelength-Multiplexed Operation of Phosphorescent White-LED Data Emitters

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Abstract:

Phosphor-converted white light emitting diodes (LED) launch a wideband visible-light spectrum suited for illumination purposes, whereas the spectral features of the light emission are determined by the blue pump source and its induced phosphorescence. Towards that, the distinctive features within the blue pump waveband are exploited to facilitate wavelength division multiplexed (WDM) data transmission for optical wireless applications that fuse lighting and communication functions. 100 Mb/s data transmission is accomplished in WDM operation with a reception penalty of 1.5 dB in optical link budget with respect to single-channel transmission. Further migration towards quaternary 200 Mb/s operation is facilitated through dual-drive LED operation. Moreover, simultaneous signaling / data transmission is demonstrated and capacity extension towards real-time data traffic transport at 303 Mb/s is shown through an adoption of multi-carrier modulation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Optical wireless communication is considered an attractive alternative to radio-frequency (RF) based data exchange due to its unique advantages with respect to unregulated spectrum and increased robustness to electro-magnetic interference [1]. As one branch of optical wireless technologies, visible light communication (VLC) builds on the re-use of luminaries specifically developed for the visible wavelength range and can thus often leverage on cost-effective light emitters [2]. Earlier accomplishments in the field of VLC have demonstrated impressive data rates beyond 25 Gb/s through use of laser-sourced lighting and communication [3].

Light emitting diodes (LED) are an ideal optical emitter candidate that has shown a continuous improvement in optical flux together with a steady decrease in device cost during the past decades, as expressed through Haitz' law [4]. The abundance of LEDs in lighting applications, for which white LEDs are often considered the prime choice, offers a convenient opportunity to seamlessly and cost-efficiently integrate VLC functionality in the consumer segment. In contrast to white micro-LEDs that are recognized for their large electro-optic bandwidth that is yet bound to a highly limited optical output at the same time [5], high-flux LEDs that are instead designed for the purpose of lighting do not resemble ideal optical transmitters: Their large active die sizes introduce bandwidth restrictions [6, 7], while in case of white LEDs the emitted optical spectrum is often a result of a phosphor-converted blue pump light, thus including slow red-shifted components. Mitigation methods that can partially address these limitations have been found through equalization and pre-emphasis involving analogue circuitry and digital signal processing (DSP) [8-14], or blue-filtered reception [10-13], leading to VLC data rates up to 3 Gb/s [13].

Spectral bonding can be additionally adopted to further the accomplished data rate of an originally "grey" VLC link with just one transmitter and one receiver. Towards that, earlier demonstrations have focused on wavelength division multiplexed (WDM) LED / laser emitters and photoreceivers [15-21]. By choosing a suitable weighting of wavelengths for the constituent WDM channels [22], the VLC system can be at the same time optimized for white-light operation [16, 17]. However, the adoption of WDM requires well-defined and well-delimited emission characteristics for the constituent data channels – a requisite that is not provided in case of white LEDs. To address this challenge, this work extends an initial analysis [23] on the adoption of WDM with phosphorescent white-LED emission, which is subject to a continuous wideband spectrum. The investigations will show that the spectral peculiarities residing in the blue pump waveband of white LEDs can be advantageously combined with blue-filtered bandwidth enhancement to facilitate multi-channel WDM transmission over a VLC link that is illuminated with multiple phosphor-converted white-LED emitters. Results obtained by means of experiment include 100 Mb/s baseband transmission, quaternary data modulation at 200 Mb/s through dual-drive operation, simultaneous low-/high-speed signaling and multi-carrier modulation enabling up to 303 Mb/s real-time transmission of Ethernet traffic.

The manuscript is organized as follows. Chapter II introduces the concept of spectral multiplexing for phosphor-converted

white LEDs, while Chapter III characterizes their electro-optic characteristics. Chapter IV discusses the evaluation framework before Chapter V investigates the VLC performance for data transmission using simple baseband modulation, including dual-drive operation and integrated low-speed signaling, as well as multi-carrier modulation. Finally, Chapter VI concludes the findings.

2. SPECTRAL MULTIPLEXING OF WHITE-LED EMISSION

A. Spectral WDM Grid in the Blue Waveband

The adoption of WDM schemes necessitates distinctive spectral features for the involved optical transmitters. While WDM is widely adopted in combination with sources that are characterized by a single optical emission frequency, white LEDs typically show a flat optical wideband spectrum. Their spectrum is specifically determined by its blue die source and its phosphorescence, whereas the weighting in blue and yellow/red components determines the correlated color temperature (CCT). In contrary to natural sunlight, the blue pump source of white LEDs is confined to a narrow spectral region. This is shown in Fig. 1, which discusses the spectral characteristics of LEDs designed for a neutral-white emission. Four commercial off-the-shelf LEDs with a luminous flux of >130 lm have been evaluated, herein denoted as LEDs **A-F** and shown in Fig. 1(a). These include the ams-OSRAM GW-CS8PM1.PM (**A**), the ams-OSRAM GW-CS8PM1.CM (**B**), the Luminus SST-20 (**C**), the Luminus MP-1616 (**D**), the Lumileds L1CU-3580 (**E**) and the Cree XPPAWT-HO (**F**). Their chromaticity is presented in Fig. 1(b) and indicates a CCT in the vicinity of 4000K apart from the outlying LED-F. Even though most LEDs have a similar CCT, their blue sources show distinctive spectral features. This is evidenced from the white-light spectrum presented in Fig. 2. When collapsing the WDM waveband of Fig. 3 over the blue region of the visible light spectrum using the filters reported in Table I, the LED sources can be allocated to different channels within a 10-nm WDM grid. Pairs of white LEDs can then be identified to facilitate WDM operation. The resulting coupling T_λ to the channels of the introduced blue-WDM grid is summarized in Fig. 4(a). An example for residual crosstalk when pairing LEDs **B** and **A** at the two WDM channels of 430 and 460 nm is shown in Fig. 4(b) in terms of detected RF spectrum for sinusoidal 50 MHz modulation of the white-LED forward currents and photodetection through an optically filtered receiver selective the corresponding WDM channel. As can be seen, a maximal RF crosstalk level of -13.9 dB originates from the second WDM channel – even through the blue pumps of both white LEDs operate simultaneously within the same waveband.

Fig. 1. (a) White LEDs employed for the VLC link and (b) their chromaticity characteristics.

Fig. 2. Spectral emission of employed white LEDs.

Fig. 3. Allocation of blue LED source to WDM channels.

Fig. 4. White-LED emission in the channels of a blue-WDM grid. (a) Optical coupling T_λ to the WDM channels, and (b) RF crosstalk as received through an optically filtered photodetector selective to a WDM channel.

WDM channel	430 nm	440 nm	450 nm	460 nm	470 nm
Characteristic					
Center wavelength λ_c [nm]	430.09	440.47	449.36	458.5	417.02
Insertion loss at λ_c [dB]	0.14	0.12	0.05	0.15	0.14
-3dB Bandwidth [nm]	9.93	9.81	10.4	9.46	10.01
Adjacent (lower, upper) channel rejection [dB]	48.6	41.6	26.2	34.5	56.2

Table I. Blue-WDM Filter Characteristics

B. Batch-to-Batch Variability of Emission Spectrum

Figure 5 discusses the batch-to-batch variability of the pump emission wavelength of the LED. Results are presented for LED-A and are based on two batches α and β with a sample size of 7 and 10 LEDs, respectively. These two batches of “identical” LEDs have been sourced through different distributors 11 months apart. The emission spectra around the peak wavelength of the blue pump is shown in Figure 5(a) and indicate similar characteristics. The corresponding histograms for both batches are presented in Fig. 5(b) for a bin width of 1 nm. First, the accumulated emission over all samples of a batch overlaps well with that of a single LED sample (dashed line), for which the first sample in the corresponding batch has been taken as a reference. This means that the variability within a batch is small. Second, the peak emission wavelengths for both batches differ by only 1 nm, as indicated through $\delta\lambda$ in Fig. 5(b). This value is well below the emission bandwidth of the LEDs, meaning that it can be seen as a negligible detuning towards the chosen WDM grid since an offset by $\delta\lambda$ would not significantly deteriorate the coupled power to the channel.

Fig. 5. (a) Emission spectra of all LED samples within the two batches α and β . (b) Histogram for the emission of all LED samples within a batch, in comparison with the emission characteristics of the first LED sample within the corresponding batch.

C. Impact of Thermal Gradients

Figure 6 further characterizes the impact of a change in operating temperature on the LED emission. A red-shift in peak wavelength can be clearly noticed in the optical spectra (Fig. 6(a)) when raising the temperature from 40 to 90°C. The actual peak wavelength is reported in Fig. 6(b) for all LED samples and shows a continuous increase at 0.08 to 0.121 nm/K. As indicated through the dashed region in Fig. 6(b), which relates to the passband of the 460-nm WDM channel, suitable LEDs such as LED-C remain within the passband over the entire temperature range from 35 to 80°C. Even if the peak wavelength exceeded the passband, the broad LED spectrum would still ensure good coupling to the WDM channel. This is because unlike laser-based emission, the optical emission spectrum of the LEDs is rather large compared to the temperature-dependent detuning. Nevertheless, a re-allocation of the WDM channel might be required to optimize crosstalk conditions in case that strong temperature gradients apply between different VLC emitters that jointly illuminate a photoreceiver. This could be implemented with multi-LED emitters that select the most suitable LED pixel – and thus emission spectrum – after determining the crosstalk, such as done in Fig. 4(b).

Fig. 6. (a) Emission spectrum of white LEDs for various operating temperatures and (b) resulting red-shift in peak emission wavelength.

3. ELECTRO-OPTIC RESPONSE OF WHITE-LED EMITTERS

The practical adoption of a WDM grid in the blue waveband might appear as a complexity burden at first glance. However, the involvement of blue-filtering is beneficial in view of a bandwidth enhancement for white-LED transmitters by suppressing slow, red-shifted phosphorus components in the received optical spectrum. This response-flattening effect is shown in Fig. 7(a), specifically for white-LED D. Without optical filter, the electro-optic response drops quickly and surpasses its 3-dB bandwidth at 0.44 MHz (\diamond). When adopting blue-filtering at 450 nm, the roll-off in the response smoothens. However, the modulation bandwidth of 3.8 MHz (\blacklozenge) remains too small to support notable transmission rates when utilizing baseband signaling without DSP support. For this reason, frequency response flattening is integrated within the RF drive path through employing an

analogue equalizer (see inset in Fig. 7(a)). The bandwidth can then be vastly extended to 105 MHz (●), which suffices 100 Mb/s transmission in combination with low-complexity two-level modulation. For comparison, it shall be noted that the unfiltered LED (◇) would have required 15 dB of extra pre-emphasis to reach the same bandwidth. Moreover, there is no significant impact on the frequency response profile when altering the WDM channel, apart from the expected change in peak magnitude of the channel response due to its sensitivity to the tilt in the spectral profile of the LED emission across several WDM channels.

Even though the adopted analogue pre-emphasis allows to flatten the highly tilted response between low and high frequencies, the intrinsic electro-optic response of the LED needs to be accounted for when addressing the RF power budget. While a saturation power of up to 30 dBm is feasible for the RF driver of the LED, the poor conversion efficiency of high-flux LEDs (and in particular white-LEDs) when modulating higher frequencies is limiting the accomplishable modulation index to very low values. This directly translates into a reception penalty for VLC transmission that is a result of the limited optical modulation amplitude (OMA). Figure 7(b) provides an exemplary on-off keyed (OOK) data pattern launched by a white LED, indicating the typical low modulation index, as discussed shortly in Section V.B.

Fig. 7. (a) Electro-optic response of white-LED D after blue-filtering and analogue equalization. The inset shows the architecture of the analogue equalizer. (b) Emitted data signal received with DC-coupled photoreceiver.

4. WDM-ENABLED WHITE-LED BROADCAST & SELECT VLC LINK

Figure 8 presents the experimental setup for WDM-enabled VLC transmission over a white-LED pair, for which two of the LEDs that have been characterized in Sections II and III are paired through a broadband beamsplitter (BS). The resulting WDM signal then illuminates a blue-enhanced receiver based on an avalanche photodiode (APD) with integrated transimpedance amplifier (TIA), which has a blue-enhanced responsivity of 32 A/W at 450 nm. An optical bandpass filter with bandwidth $\delta\lambda$ is inserted before the APD to evaluate WDM operation by selecting spectral components within one of the WDM channels. A neutral density (ND) filter further sets the optical budget (OB) for the lab-scale VLC link with a distance of 3.2 m between the white-LED emitters and the APD receiver. Beam collimation and light collection is supported through 2" lens optics at the transmitters and receiver, respectively.

Two modulation schemes are considered for the data transmitter. First, baseband modulation utilizing OOK represents a simplified scheme that nevertheless requires a flat channel response to enable DSP-free VLC transmission. In this primary setting, a pseudo-random bit sequence is generated by an arbitrary waveform generator (AWG), to drive the LED emitter that integrates the earlier discussed analogue equalizer stage in its RF drive path. The received signal is then forwarded to bit error ratio (BER) testing and further digitized for signal analysis. As an alternative scenario, multi-carrier transmission is investigated as a second, capacity-generating data transmission scheme. For this DSP-assisted mode, a G.hn test-set (MaxLinear DCP962C) drives the unequalized white-LED emitter with an up to 200-MHz wide multi-carrier signal that is adaptively modulated based on the overall link response and inter-channel crosstalk. The return channel of the G.hn link was implemented through an electrical back-to-back connection and is not evaluated during performance assessment. Moreover, the channel capacity and stability are experimentally investigated through real-time Ethernet-based traffic emulation.

Finally, a second, unfiltered APD+TIA receiver is additionally employed to investigate the simultaneous signaling and data transmission over the VLC link, which is again based on simple OOK modulation, yet using asymmetric data rates.

Fig. 8. Experimental setup to evaluate a WDM-enabled multi-emitter VLC link based on phosphor-converted, white-LED technology.

5. VLC TRANSMISSION PERFORMANCE

First, the reception performance has been evaluated using baseband modulation with the simple two-level OOK format. Next, the penalty due to WDM operation is assessed, before a dual-drive scheme is employed to facilitate a higher OMA and quaternary data transmission. Moreover, the integration of lower-rate signaling is investigated. The use of multi-carrier modulation and its performance for WDM operation concludes the VLC performance evaluation.

A. OOK Baseband Transmission and WDM Operation

The BER performance for single-channel OOK transmission at 450 nm with white-LED **B** is presented in Fig. 9(a). Results are reported for various spectral cut-off frequencies that result from blue filtering with a variable filter bandwidth $\delta\lambda$, using a pseudo-random bit sequence of length 2^7-1 at a rate of 100 Mb/s. Two filtering effects can be clearly noticed: First, an increased filter width leads to an error floor since it passes the slower red components (Fig. 2). This degradation applies for a cut-off of 550 nm (\blacklozenge) and higher. Second, if the filter is chosen with a too narrow bandwidth of $\delta\lambda = 10$ nm, equivalent to a cut-off at 455 nm (\blacktriangle), a substantial loss in optical power is introduced, as summarized in Fig. 9(b). This filtering loss, which amounts to 6.8 dB when changing between the bandwidths of $\delta\lambda = 50$ nm (\bullet) and 10 nm (\blacktriangle), translates into a reduced OB that can be supported for the VLC link. The margin for the 3.2-m VLC link is still 4.3 dB at a BER of 10^{-9} . Figure 9(b) shows that the optimum transmission performance is found for a cut-off at 475 nm ($\delta\lambda = 50$ nm). However, this setting for the filter bandwidth is too broad to accommodate multiple WDM channels. This leads to the conclusion that WDM operation with the given white-LED spectra will be intrinsically bound to a reduction in supported OB.

Figure 9(c) reports the BER performance at 100 Mb/s under such WDM operation. Comparison is further made with single-channel transmission ($\square, \diamond, \triangle, \circ$) using the same blue-filter bandwidth of $\delta\lambda = 10$ nm. When pairing white-LEDs **A** and **B** at the two adjacent WDM channels at 440 nm (\blacklozenge) and 450 nm (\blacktriangle), WDM crosstalk leads to a penalty of 5.8 dB (\blacklozenge, \diamond) and 4.4 dB ($\blacktriangle, \triangle$) at a BER of 10^{-3} when referencing to the single-channel transmission at the respective wavelengths. To reduce this penalty, a wider channel spacing of 30 nm has been additionally investigated. This operation, which skips two WDM channels in between, now utilizes the pair of white-LEDs **A** and **C** at 430 nm (\blacksquare) and 460 nm (\bullet), respectively. The reception penalty now reduces to 1.5 and 1.1 dB as a direct result of the spectral guard channels. This proves that two-channel WDM operation is in principle compatible with the spectral configuration of white high-flux LED emitters.

Fig. 9. (a) BER performance for single-channel operation for various blue filters and (b) minimal achievable BER and compatible optical budget for the VLC link. (c) BER performance under WDM operation for two white-LED pairs.

B. Reception Penalty due to Reduced Modulation Index

Due to RF drive limitations, the modulation index of the emitted data signal is typically low. Figure 10 investigates the impact of the reduced intensity modulation extinction. At full drive, the modulation index m of 0.33 enables a BER of 10^{-9} at an OB of 3.9 dB (●). When deliberately reducing the RF drive to emulate lower modulation indices, the reception performance worsens due to a reduced eye opening. This introduces a reception penalty Π in terms of compatible link budget. This penalty is indicated in Fig. 9(a) for a BER level of 10^{-3} and is referenced to the full-drive condition ($m = 0.33$), for which it is 0 dB. Specifically, a penalty of 6.8 dB applies when the modulation index drops to 0.11 (■). Figure 10(b) further estimates the improvement in OB that could be potentially accomplished when provisioning a more powerful RF drive, thus increasing the modulation index m . For this, comparison is made to the expected reception penalty ξ due to a reduced modulation index, which is

$$\xi = \frac{2}{m} - 1 \quad (1)$$

The experimental data for Π fits well to the model for ξ . Figure 10(b) further shows that an improved RF drive supporting $m = 0.5$ would allow to allocate an additional optical budget of 2.3 dB for the VLC link.

C. Dual-Drive Operation and PAM4 Transmission

The benefits due to dual-drive operation of a white LED emitter are demonstrated through Fig. 11(a), which reports single-channel VLC transmission with white-LED **D** for its operation at the 450-nm channel. First, by differentially driving both, anode and cathode of the white LED emitter (δ in Fig. 8), the OMA can be doubled, which leads to an increase in supported OB by 6.1 dB. Alternatively, dual-drive configuration with independent tributary data streams enables higher-order baseband modulation such as quaternary pulse amplitude modulation (PAM4). Figure 11(a) includes the corresponding BER performance for 200 Mb/s PAM4 transmission (▲) after off-line multi-level symbol slicing. A BER below the forward error correction (FEC) limit at 10^{-3} is accomplished for an OB of 3.1 dB. With this, the dual-drive emitter allows for a rate-adaptive VLC transmission that optimizes the channel capacity according to the link budget – without deviating from a low-complexity two-level electrical driving scheme and thus while resorting to VLC link operation in a DSP-free manner.

Fig. 10. (a) BER performance as function of the modulation index and (b) resulting reception penalty.

D. Integration of Lower-Rate Signaling

The dual-drive scheme further allows for high-speed (HS) data transmission with simultaneous low-speed (LS) signaling. Such a configuration can re-use the same optical spectrum to convey two independent signals in applications where services call for highly asymmetric data rates. The 100-Mb/s HS OOK signal has been 8B10B-coded, resulting in a line rate of 125 Mb/s to permit the transmission of a 5-Mb/s LS signal. Reception is then conducted with two distinct VLC receivers (Fig. 8), for which only that detecting the HS data applies blue-filtering (at 450 nm, $\delta\lambda = 10$ nm), while the second photodetector receives the full white-LED spectrum without filtering loss.

Fig. 11. (a) BER performance for dual-drive LED operation to extend optical budget or facilitate PAM4 coding. (b) Received data signals for LS signaling integrated with HS data transmission, including the RF spectrum of the HS data channel. (c) HS BER performance and LS Q-factor for simultaneous LS signaling / HS data transmission.

Figure 11(b) presents examples for received signal traces at the photodetectors devoted to LS and HS signal reception. The electrically unfiltered time-domain signal and RF spectrum of the HS signal shows an impact of simultaneous LS signaling on the HS data envelope. The corresponding BER performance for HS and LS VLC transmission is discussed in Fig. 11(c), whereas reference is made to the ratio ξ between the OMAs for LS and HS signals. The Q-factor of the LS signaling directly depends on the choice for its OMA_{LS} (○). There is little degradation due to simultaneous HS data transmission (●) since simple low-pass filtering can cater for its suppression. The reception performance for HS data transmission without simultaneous LS signaling shows that the additional extension in data signal bandwidth due to line coding is leading to a BER floor at 1.3×10^{-5} (□). This is explained by the widened signal spectrum that exceeds the flat region within the electro-optic response of the blue-filtered white LED (Fig. 7). A larger penalty is introduced for the HS data reception in case of simultaneous HS + LS VLC transmission (■), leading to a BER beyond 10^{-2} for a setting of $\xi = 0.7$. However, the crosstalk that arises due to the LS channel can be effectively suppressed when applying additional high-pass filtering with a cut-on frequency of 4 MHz (◆). The BER of the HS channel then approaches the performance for exclusive HS data transmission, leaving just a small residual penalty that is determined by the OMA of the LS data signal. This enables an optimization of ξ to jointly improve both VLC channels. By doing so, a Q-factor beyond 6 can be obtained for the 5 Mb/s LS signaling channel, while a BER below 10^{-3} can be accomplished for net-100 Mb/s HS data transmission – both of which are achieved at point Ξ in Fig. 11(c). At this setting, which yields $\xi = 0.8$, the OMA for LS

signaling is slightly lower than that for HS data transmission.

It shall be stressed that the low-frequency cut-off introduced through the adopted drive scheme that involves a bias-T can negatively impact the transmission performance of the LS channel. A DC-coupled RF driver can be employed to mitigate this effect. Suitable drivers have been demonstrated for linear operation and integrated signal pre-emphasis [24].

E. Multi-Carrier Data Transmission

Finally, multi-carrier modulation has been applied to probe the possibility for higher data rates and their robustness to WDM crosstalk. Due to the adoption of adaptive modulation, no analogue equalizer has been included in the RF driver path of the white LEDs for the purpose of response flattening. Figure 12 presents the received signal spectra when using white-LED **D** as optical single-channel emitter, with no extra optical attenuation in the VLC link – neither due to an insertion of ND filters, nor due to the optical beamsplitter. The spectra further show the noise level of the dark APD photoreceiver and that for the photo-generated shot-noise due to a DC-biased white-LED emitter (without data signal). There is a good contrast of 33.5 dB at lower frequencies, which reduces to a level of 4.1 dB towards the upper sub-carriers of G.hn signal as the electro-optic response of the LD rolls off. The corresponding signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) spectra that can be obtained for single-channel transmission and WDM operation are reported in Fig. 13(a) and Fig. 13(b) for operation at 460 nm (LED **D**) and 430 nm (LED **A**), respectively. Despite the insertion of the beamsplitter in the VLC path, a peak SNR of 28.5 and 27.5 dB can be accomplished under single-channel operation at these two WDM channels. The corresponding data rate that can be achieved is presented in Fig. 13(c). Without ND filter, single-channel rates of 295 Mb/s (\blacktriangle) and 248 Mb/s (\bullet) are obtained at the 460 and 430 nm WDM channel, respectively. These rates drop to 150 and 104 Mb/s for an optical VLC budget of 6 dB.

Fig. 12. RF spectra of received G.hn signal and noise background due to dark photodetector and unmodulated white LED.

When activating the second WDM channel that is fed by the AWG with a multi-carrier signal having the same signal bandwidth, crosstalk reduces the SNR according to the finite suppression of the blue-pump emission at the second WDM channel. This causes the peak SNR to reduce to 14.3 and 14.8 dB at the 460 and 430 nm channel, respectively. The data rate under WDM operation is appended to Fig. 13(c). It reduces from 295 to 121 Mb/s (\triangle) and from 248 to 122 Mb/s (\circ) at 460 and 430 nm, respectively. Still, these rates are clearly above the 100 MB/s rates obtained for OOK modulation.

Lastly, Ethernet data has been transported over the VLC link. Figure 14 shows the data throughput R for single-channel operation at 460 nm, without extra optical loss in the VLC link (\square in Fig. 13(c)). The link capacity remains steady at an average of 303 Mb/s over the entire measurement duration of more than 90 minutes and shows just a few excursions that are attributed to buffering artifacts at the traffic-generating end-points rather than to instabilities of the VLC link.

Fig. 13. SNR spectra for single- and dual-channel operation at the (a) 460-nm and (b) 430-nm WDM channels. (c) G.hn data rate as function of optical budget at the VLC link.

Fig. 14. Provisioned Ethernet data rate over single-channel VLC link operated at 460 nm.

6. LASER-SOURCED WHITE-LIGHT EMITTERS

The broad pump emission spectrum of white LEDs leads to crosstalk at adjacent WDM channels, which together with the spectral width of the blue waveband limits the number of WDM channels that can be practically implemented. The spectrally narrow pump emission of laser-sourced white LEDs can mitigate crosstalk while enabling a better scalability for signal multiplexing. Figure 15 emphasizes this advantage by comparing traditional white-LED emission, as given for LED-B, with white light generated through a laser-pumped phosphorus light source (L). Results are shown as optical emission power normalized to the spectral peak component and for a configuration that utilizes a 450 nm laser diode. As Fig. 15 insidactes, the laser pump spectrum is confined and does not extend beyond the corresponding WDM channel passband while it generates white light with a similar characteristic than LED-B. Such a spectral setup is touted as promising candidate to realize a crosstalk-optimized multi-channel WDM scheme suitable for white-light emitters that additionally feature bandwidth-enhanced VLC functionality.

Fig. 15. Emission spectra for a traditional white-light source based on LED-B and a laser-sourced white-light emitter (L), aligned against the transmission function of a blue-waveband WDM channel.

7. CONCLUSION

WDM operation has been introduced in combination with white-LED emission. Successful 100 Mb/s transmission at two blue WDM channels has proven the compatibility of commercial high-flux emitters for joint illumination and VLC in scenarios where multiple optical emitters illuminate the scene. Moreover, the dual-drive operation of these LEDs has been shown to facilitate either a higher OB for the VLC link or the adoption of PAM4 signaling, both of which are aspects that can be beneficial for rate/distance adaptive deployment scenarios. Simultaneous LS/HS signaling at asymmetric data rates can further cater for highly varying traffic demands that emerge from different service requirements. Finally, a capacity extension has been demonstrated by an adoption of multi-carrier modulation provided through readily available G.hn technology, facilitating real-time Ethernet data transmission at 303 Mb/s. Further improvement of the VLC performance in terms of operable WDM channels and transmission capacity is expected when migrating to blue pump sources with improved spectral confinement, as it exemplarily applies to laser-sourced white-light emitters.

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